

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Mapping an Impact Network for Transformational Change in CLEVER

Deliverable 8.1

Summary

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Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
INTRODUCTION.....	5
OBJECTIVES	6
METHODS	7
RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	10
CONCLUSIONS	21
PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED	23
REFERENCES	24

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents supply chain stakeholder maps to be used for CLEVER project consultations. It includes stakeholder maps that represent the trade supply chains of (i) timber and soy in Brazil, (ii) timber in Cameroon, and (iii) fishmeal and fish oil on a global scale, and their respective flows towards the EU. The addressed groups include biomass producers, processors, traders, retailers, civil society organisations, certifying bodies, research institutions, and policymakers. The aim is to ensure participation or consideration of a diverse group of representatives in project consultations, to facilitate knowledge transfer, enable their contribution to refine the project's vision, and empower them through the co-design process for innovative governance instruments.

The mapping was based on surveys and interviews with experts, to identify a diversity of stakeholders critical to the supply chains, considering where the project partners have existing relationships and therefore greater chance of engagement. The maps represent a non-exhaustive portrayal of the supply chains that aims to bring together a diversity of stakeholders for collaboration and co-design.

The value chains examined feature structural differences in terms of the scale, horizontal integration, and formality of their activities, among others. These may be used to identify leverage points for impactful governance mechanisms. The stakeholder mapping exercise consulted local partners and research institutions to bring a balance of actors from both exporting and importing countries, including smaller civil society and specialised research organisations. Particular attention was paid to the involvement of local communities and vulnerable groups directly or indirectly affected by trade. Further efforts were made to enhance gender representation.

This work has laid the foundations of the next project phases that will develop in-depth and comprehensive value chain maps detailing the stages of value chains and the policy instruments that influence them and engage with CLEVER's impact network as a primary source of information for empirical research. The mapping also contributes particularly to the Dissemination, Engagement, and Communication targets of the project.

INTRODUCTION

Today's globalized trade supply chains have the ability to cause habitat degradation far away from the place of consumption. Demand in the global north exerts pressure over the global south's ecosystems with international trade representing around 30% of all threats to species globally (Lenzen et al., 2012). Habitat conversion through agriculture land use and forestry are key drivers of this threat and lie at the core of some of the most important globally traded commodities (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2019). Resolving this issue requires an overhaul of the international instruments governing today's diffused global supply chains (LeBaron, Lister & Dauvergne, 2017). Moreover, this adds up to the broader sustainability challenge of transforming global economies towards circular bio-economies.

However, the negative biodiversity trend caused by habitat conversion for production can be transformed into a positive trend if science-based, ambitious, and coordinated strategies are implemented (Leclère et al., 2020). At the EU level, the effectiveness of current instruments to generate binding and enforceable results have room for improvement (Bellora et al., 2020). CLEVER seeks to identify new leverage points to enable a sustainable transformation of the policy instruments governing Europe's and the world's trade regimes. It aims to co-design ideas and value propositions for innovative interventions and governance arrangements based on improved supply chain knowledge. For this purpose, the project intends to improve the understanding of how biomass trade is linked to biodiversity impacts and co-benefits; and to provide empirical evidence for causal relationships between supply chain governance instruments and biodiversity impacts, as well as related policy spillovers.

The trade of soy, timber, and fishmeal are addressed with regional foci laying on EU trade with South America and Central Africa, where some of the world's largest high conservation value (HCV) areas are threatened by current and expected future biomass production and extraction (IPBES 2019). CLEVER aims to engage key groups across value chains via co-design: as a participatory design-thinking process using practical tools to facilitate and enable innovation (Blomkamp, 2018), thus supporting the generation of innovative and validated results that are relevant for stakeholders and decision-makers (Pulido-Velazquez et al., 2023).

OBJECTIVES

This document (8.1) presents stakeholder maps for soy, timber, and fishmeal/oil trade. It covers soy originating from Brazil; timber from both Cameroon and Brazil, and fishmeal is approached globally. Stakeholders included in these maps cover the producer-to-procurement segments and represent a selection of actors relevant for participation in co-design processes for policy analysis and design.

The CLEVER project will convene a flexible core group of stakeholders to facilitate prompt and effective engagement and allow us to collaborate with a diverse and integrated set of representatives. This sample of actors represents an extended vision of the project's partners and their established links to engage with key agents for change.

CLEVER's impact network aims to:

1. Enable the participation of a diverse group of representatives from supply chains, as well as policymakers, academia, and research, certifying bodies, and civil society organisations for them to contribute to refining the assumptions, hypotheses and modelling scenarios of the project.
2. Facilitate knowledge transfer across partners and allow for stakeholders to become key informants for empirical research
3. Include and empower agents of change through the co-design process for innovative policy recommendations and governance instruments.

The mapping seeks to be country specific, gender-balanced, to distinguish between the different supply chains, and to allow for gender-sensitive theories of change which will be regularly updated as new knowledge becomes available through stakeholder engagement. Care is also taken to include vulnerable and indirectly affected groups as well as civil society representatives.

Overall, this mapping will allow CLEVER to correspondingly engage with those target groups that are most relevant to enact transformative change. It is closely aligned with CLEVER's Objective 3 as it seeks to facilitate the co-designed modelling of frameworks for supply chain governance initiatives and enhance their impact by focusing on groups whose support is critical for transformation.

METHODS

Mapping an Impact Network

In order to analyse system and supply chain level dynamics, and to facilitate and enable R&I co-design, this document maps a non-exhaustive group of stakeholders that represents the trade supply chain in biomass exporting and importing countries. These stakeholders include biomass producers, processors, traders, retailers, civil society organisations, certifying bodies, research institutions, and policymakers. For this purpose, external stakeholders are understood as groups and organizations that have an interest in the project and who may affect or be affected by its outcomes or impacts (PMI, 2017).

Using a qualitative approach to data collection, this mapping draws upon information collected by surveying 13 experts collaborating in CLEVER, along with subsequent in-depth interviews with key country researchers. The survey instruments were supply chain and country specific. This group of advisors brings together experts in economic, trade, and policy analysis with environmental and natural scientists in a transdisciplinary research design. In addition, the mapping leverages existing research and knowledge networks from the UKRI GCRF Trade, Development and the Environment Hub led by UNEP-WCMC, interviewing practitioners and researchers with agendas closely aligned with CLEVER. The individual and multi-stakeholder platforms that provided letters of interest in the proposal stage were also included. The criteria for inclusion in the extended network considered; (i) the need to engage with target groups that are most relevant to enact transformative change according to expert advice; (ii) links to previously established networks by the project's teams to facilitate consultation; and (iii) relevant stakeholders that already manifested their willingness to engage with CLEVER.

Now, even though some supply chains possess private arrangements for multi-stakeholder governance (e.g., roundtables), these alone tend to fall short on deliberative democracy criteria like inclusiveness and consequentiality (Shouten, Leroy & Glabsbergen, 2012). At the same time, the spotlight given to supply chains exposes the project to male-dominated stakeholder representation, especially at the level of biomass producers, processors, and traders (Nakazibwe and Pelupessy 2014). Consequently, and considering gender equality and diversity can have an influence in negotiations around policy proposals and stakeholder platforms (Boyer et al. 2009), the stakeholder mapping was complemented with a wider variety of groups to achieve the inclusiveness that CLEVER's holistic approach entails. Therefore, particular emphasis is given to ensure equal gender representation in the co-design process -focusing on women who are excluded or disadvantaged in relation to decision-making and access to economic and social resources. In addition, the mapping put an effort to consider vulnerable and indirectly affected groups as well as civil society representatives to take part in future consultations.

To analyse and segment the supply chain stages, a hybrid framework compiled from UNDP (2017) and Rautner, Legger & Davis (2013) is suggested. The framework compiled considers both (i) the need to identify a core group of stakeholders that will facilitate prompt and effective engagement thus reducing the resolution of supply chain maps and generating broader categories, and (ii) revisions from expert advisors that aimed to allow the segments to be more detailed. Furthermore, additional groupings were added to allow for the inclusion of policymakers, academia, and research, certifying bodies, and civil society organisations. The resulting abridged network map framework can be found below.

Figure 1: Abridged Network Map Framework

According to the conceptual framework underlying CLEVER's system-level perspective, the components of supply, demand, and trade, each tend to be value-chain-specific due to product characteristics and historically grown trade relationships. Therefore, the regional focuses for soy (South America) and timber (Central Africa and South America) are mapped independently through the lens of the focal point countries in Brazil and Cameroon respectively, while fishmeal is approached globally given the broader geographical range of the stakeholders identified.

Participatory Impact Pathways Analysis: An Engagement Strategy

The engagement of stakeholders in consultation and co-design processes will be a long-term endeavour representing a direct and primary input for CLEVER's forthcoming outputs 8.3: *Stakeholder consultations on project workplan, theory of change, and co-design*; and 7.1: *Co-designed modelling framework for supply chain governance initiatives*. For this purpose, and to deliver on the objectives through a formulated framework, an adapted Participatory Impact Pathways Analysis (PIPA) is adopted as an engagement methodology.

PIPA is a practical approach that can be used for stakeholder engagement where groups involved in a project make explicit their assumptions and how they expect it to deliver impact. It has been used in settings seeking to enable institutional learning and facilitates the establishment of ex-ante prioritization strategies and ex-post evaluation and assessment (Alvarez et al., 2010). The methodology has been designed for multi-sectorial, multi-stakeholder, and international large-scale projects, and can be adapted to different time-spans and budget conditions (STEPS, 2023).

Figure 2: Stages in PIPA Methodology

Adapted from Alvarez, 2010, p. 949.

PIPA involves practical workshops where stakeholders collectively construct a theory of change for the project. It starts with the development of a Problem Tree that helps to understand shared problems and shed light on different approaches to resolve them according to the various stakeholders' perspectives. An action plan is later established followed by the identification of groups that must be involved to achieve change – building a network map (Fox & Kniveton, 2019). As a next step, an Outcomes Logic Model (i.e., Impact Pathways) is collectively proposed. In CLEVER, this is an ideal scenario for stakeholders to contribute to co-designed and gender sensitive theories of change.

Ultimately, the goal is to design a collective response to the problem trees identified, generating co-designed supply chain governance initiatives that enhance biodiversity conservation and co-benefits. These discussions will be bolstered and accompanied by CLEVER's findings for (i) causal relationships between value chain governance initiatives and biodiversity impacts and related spillovers, and (ii) links bet biomass trade, biodiversity impacts and co-benefits in exporting and importing regions. Figure 2 showcases the main steps in this PIPA adaptation and the prospective steps to apply it in CLEVER.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping CLEVER's Impact Networks

Stakeholder groups were clustered primarily based on their role in the supply chain, the country of origin (Brazil, Cameroon, or other/international), and the commodity they were involved in (timber, soy, fishmeal/fish oil). A compilation of information about the identified organisations is presented in an Excel database (Appendix 1), which contains the potential stakeholders for engagement and a short description of their agenda. Table 1 showcases the goals for engagement for each category identified in the mapping, separating specific and common outlooks.

Table 1. Stakeholder groups and goals for engagement

Stakeholder group	Specific goals for engagement	Interconnected goals for engagement
Production	To engage groups at production stages of supply chains holistically to improve understanding of the social impact of policies with local communities and their effects on producers while ensuring equal gender representation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Enable participation and co-design ✓ Improve legitimacy of solutions proposed
Processing	To engage groups at various processing stages in supply chains to generate knowledge on their role in trade and procurement, and their potential contribution as actors of change.	
Trade & Distribution	To engage groups at the trade and distribution levels as a primary source for data in value chain mapping and as a funnel stage for interventions.	
Retail & Consumption	To engage with retailers to develop business cases, value propositions, and proofs of concept for candidate intervention proposals.	
Civil Society Organisations	To engage Civil Society Organisations alike grassroots small producers' associations, women	

	associations, or environmental NGOs to encourage the participation of civil society. They will contribute to refining the assumptions, hypotheses, and modelling scenarios to maximize relevance, credibility, diversity, and legitimacy.	✓ Ensure higher relevance and impact of solutions proposed
Certifying Bodies	To engage certifying bodies as non-state governance mechanisms to better understand their potential roles in terms of positive transformative change in policy, markets, behaviour, and environmental protection.	
Research & Universities	To bring together research bodies and universities to provide empirical evidence for causal relationships between trade and biodiversity impacts improving the understanding of their links to co-benefits, governance initiatives, and policy spillovers. To participate in and guide the practical workshops for co-design and collaborative problem-solving.	
Policy level	To engage policy level groups to maximize relevance of co-designed solutions and involve key actors for transformative change.	

Stakeholder Maps

Soy & Timber in Brazil

For the Brazilian supply chain stakeholder map, this mapping collaborated with CLEVER partners, including the Federal University of Pará, the Federal University of Minas Gerais, CEBRAP, the University of Freiburg, and the networks within the GCRF Centre for Trade, Development and Environment Hub (GCRF TRADE Hub), which included researchers in the Department of Agriculture, Political Science, and Development at the University of Reading and UNEP-WCMC colleagues. The outcome can be found below in Figure 3.

Figure 3: CLEVER's impact network for soy and timber trade focused on Brazil. The green background indicates that the group is related to soy, and blue is used for timber. Organisations relevant to both commodities are marked in grey.

Abbreviations in the figure: **Civil Society Organisations:** CIMI (The Indigenist Missionary Council); MIQBC (The Interstate Movement of Babassu Coconut Breakers of Maranhão, Pará, Piauí and Tocantins); MMC (Peasant Women's Movement); IPAM (The Amazon Environmental Research Institute); COIAB (Coordination of the Indigenous Organizations of the Brazilian Amazon); CTI (Indigenous Work Centre); ISA (Socio-Environmental Institute); FETRAF-Brazil (The National Federation of Men and Women Family Farming Workers); GTS (Grupo de Trabalho da Soja); CONTAG (National Confederation of Workers in Agriculture); **Certifying Bodies:** FSC (Forest Stewardship Council); RTRS (Round Table on Responsible Soy); **Production:** COOMFLONA (Flona Tapajos Joint Cooperative); CONFLORESTA (Brazilian Association of Forestry Concessionary Companies); **Processing:** Abiove (the Brazilian Association of Vegetable Oil Industries.); Abimci (Brazilian Association for Mechanically Processed Timber); OVID (Association of the Oilseed Processing Industry in Germany); **Trade & Distribution:** Aimex (Association of the Wood Exporting Industries of the State of Pará); Ibá (Brazilian Tree Industry); ETTF (European Timber Trade Federation); **Retail & Consumption:** DVT (The German Animal Food Association); CGF (Consumer Goods Forum); **Research & Universities:** UFMG (Federal University of Minas Gerais); UFPA (Federal University of Pará); UFG (Federal University of Goiás); INPA (National Institute of Amazonian Research); Cebrap (Brazilian Centre of Analysis and Planning); Embrapa (Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation); **Policy Level:** MAPA (Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock); MDA (Ministry of Agrarian Development); MMULHERES (Ministry of Women); MIP (Ministry of Indigenous Peoples); FUNAI (National Indian Foundation); MPF (Federal Prosecution Office); BLE (German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture); APD (German-Brazilian Agricultural Policy Dialogue)

Production

A broad inquiry into the Brazilian context suggests that in the septentrional and western regions, soy is mostly grown on large-scale, industrial, single-crop farms; with small farmers and producer associations being less predominant there as they are located mostly in the south. Relevant groups considered in this stage include Aprosoja, Brazil's largest soy producer association. In the case of timber producers, the mapping identified the COOMFLONA cooperative, which has 269 organisation members, and CONFLOREST, a group of 11 forest concessionaires. Both claim to produce wood in a conscious, managed, and sustainable way, minimising the irregular exploitation of forest resources with local communities.

Processing

Relevant groups include Bom Futuro, the world's largest producer of soybeans whose operation is located in Mato Grosso. As well, the Brazilian Vegetable Oil Industry Association (ABIOVE) has a strong sustainability agenda and is a party to the Soy Moratorium Trade Agreement, which has committed not to trade or finance soy produced in the forested areas of the Amazon biome. The Association of the Oilseed Processing Industry in Germany, a member of CLEVER's initial reference group, represents importers in this stage of the value chain. For timber, the Brazilian Mechanically Processed Wood Industry Association (ABIMCI) is identified as an entry point for the category.

Trade & Distribution

In trade and distribution, potential stakeholders for engagement in the soy supply chain mainly consist of actors mapped through the GCRF TRADE Hub, including big multinational corporations such as ADM, Bunge, and Cargill. For timber, we incorporate the Wood Exporting Industries of the State of Pará (AIMEX), the Brazilian Tree Industry (Ibá), and the European Timber Trade Federation (ETTF).

Retail & Consumption

The retail and consumption stage includes examples of interested businesses and business initiatives that have previously provided public consultations and supplementary opinions on issues related to deforestation regulation in other contexts. LIDL has also manifested their interest in CLEVER previously, and Otto Group is a member of the project's initial reference group.

Civil Society Organisations

The Civil Society Organizations segment contains representatives of environmental initiatives, such as the Amazon Environmental Research Institute (IPAM), groups working for local and indigenous peoples such as the Coordination of the Indigenous Organizations of the Brazilian Amazon (COIAB), and organizations that advocate for farmers, workers, and women, such as the National Confederation of Workers in Agriculture (CONTAG) and the Mulheres do Agronegocio forum, among others.

Certifying Bodies

Certifying bodies, including FSC, the Round Table on Responsible Soy (RTRS), and the ProTerra Foundation, a non-profit organization that promotes the sustainability of feed and food production, are significant actors. The ProTerra Network is particularly strong in Brazil, with 14 certified companies.

Research & Universities

There are several federal universities in Brazil, such as the Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG) and the Federal University of Pará (UFPA), which are CLEVER partners. The Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation Embrapa has research units for soy and forests in the Amazonian region. The Brazilian Centre of Analysis and Planning (CEBRAP) is a global research centre and think tank that has connections to institutions and civil society associations in the country. They have also participated in the development of the Brazil stakeholder map.

Policy level

The policy landscape in relation to Brazilian supply chains can be divided into three levels: regional or municipal, federal, and transnational. At the regional level, there is a plethora of relevant actors, but the Interstate Consortium for Sustainable Development of The Legal Amazon Region is highlighted as a key regional actor in the Amazonia. At the federal level, relevant ministries include Agriculture and Livestock, Agrarian Development, Women, and Indigenous Peoples. In the EU context, The Directorate Generals of the European Commission for Trade and Environment are considered, along with the German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BLE) and the German-Brazilian Agricultural Policy Dialogue (ADP) that represent European national organisations on agriculture and trade.

Timber in Cameroon

Along with the surveyed experts, consultations with the University of Dschang (FASA) in Cameroon and the European Forest Institute (EFI) provided information for key groups in the Cameroonian timber sector. Both institutions are currently developing a comprehensive Cameroon-EU timber value chain map. An initial draft indicates various formal and informal timber sources, as well as different routes by which the wood material flows and transforms in the country of production. The core idea of this stakeholder map is aligned with the draft value chain map provided by CLEVER's partners while maintaining a stronger focus on secondary and tertiary actors around the value chain (i.e., civil society organisations or policy makers). The result can be found below in Figure 4.

According to initial blueprints developed by FASA, the Cameroon timber supply chain can be divided into two main categories of formal and informal sectors. The formal sector is governed in accordance with the country's legal and regulatory provisions, it is mainly made up of an upstream of large logging companies that are authorized by law to carry out the first stages of processing, such as sawing of logs into timber and veneer. There are 200 legally registered wood processing companies in the country out of which two-thirds are large industries that are involved in primary processing of wood. The remaining third - belonging to small and medium size enterprises - involved in secondary processing - and others working in wood transformation (joinery, doors, cladding, furniture, etc.) mainly in the informal sector. A significant part of the country's forestry sector is confined to informality due to a difficult and often unsuitable operating environment at all stages of exploitation such as: harvesting, processing, and trading of wood products. To supply the informal network of several thousand of micro enterprises and timber traders, part of the lumber would necessarily be from irregular sources, with temporary sawmills operating in the forest and delivering the sawn timber to centralised cargo terminals by makeshift transport networks.

Civil Society Organizations

Certifying Bodies

Production

Processing*

Trade & Distribution

Retail & Consumption

Research & Universities

Policy level

State Actors

International Actors, Technical Institutions

Figure 4: CLEVER's impact network for timber trade focused on Cameroon. Processing*: Many businesses listed under the 'Production' stage of the supply chain operate also at the next stages of processing of wood. Therefore, they have not been shown as duplicates in the stakeholder map.

Abbreviations in the figure: **Civil Society Organisations:** ECODEV (Ecosystems and Development); CAM-ECOLOGY (Cameroon Ecology); CED (Centre for Environment & Rural Development); FODER (Forestry and Rural Development); FLAG (Field Legality Advisory Group); CEW (Cameroon Environmental Watch); CASuDEV (Community Association for Sustainable Development); APIFED (Support for the self-help and integration of women, youth and the unemployed); REFACOF (African Women's Network for Community Management of Forests); IUCN (The International Union for Conservation of Nature); FECAPROBOIS (The Cameroonian Federation of Associations and Practitioners of Second Timber Processing); WWF (World Wide Fund for Nature); GFBS (Cameroon Timber Industry Association); **Certifying Bodies:** OLB (Origine et Légalité des Bois); FSC (Forest Stewardship Council); **Retail & Consumption:** CGF (Consumer Goods Forum); **Research and Universities:** FASA (University of Dschang); IRAD (Institute of Agricultural Research for Development); CIRAD (The French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development); EFI (European Forest Institute); CIFOR (Centre for International Forestry Research); IRD (Institute of Research for Development); ENEF MBALMAYO (National Forestry School); IUT MBALMAYO (University Institute of Wood Technology); CRESA FORET BOIS (Regional Centre for Specialised Education in Forestry and Wood Agriculture in Yaoundé); **Policy level:** MINFOF (Ministry of Forests and Wildlife - Republic of Cameroon); MINEPDED (Ministry of Environment, Nature Protection and Sustainable Development); ANAFOR (National Forestry Development Agency); MINFI (Institutional Site for Ministry of Finance); MINESUP (Ministry of Higher Education); CBP (Timber Promotion Centre); BMN (Enterprise Upgrading Bureau); MINEFOP (Ministry of Employment and Vocational Training); MINCOMMERCE (Ministry of Trade); COMIFAC (Commission for Central African Forests); MINPMEESA (Ministry of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises, Social Economy and Handicrafts); GIZ-KfW (German Society for International Cooperation- KfW Development Bank); ATIBT (International Tropical Timber Technical Association)

Production

Drawing on contextual insights from FASA, the mapping lists timber production businesses, classifying them as small and medium, large national, and transnational. The platform Open Timber Portal provides a comprehensive list of timber sector operators and supported this task. Notable actors here include the Pallisco logging operator that already has 10 partnerships with both national and international institutions and cooperation agencies.

Processing

Many businesses listed under the 'Production' stage of the supply chain operate also at the next stages of processing of wood. Therefore, they have not been shown as duplicates in the stakeholder map.

Trade & Distribution

The downstream of wood production is structured around actors that operate as exporters and traders of raw and processed wood. These actors are mainly located in the port cities of Douala and Kribi. Examples include Cameroon Timber Shipping Company and Cameroon Timber Export Sarl. This category also covers road, rail, and maritime transporters of logs and processed wood products which will be surveyed at later stages of the EFI/University of Dschang value chain mapping.

Retail & Consumption

The stakeholders listed on the Retail & Consumption stage are examples of potentially interested businesses and business initiatives. Examples include LIDL, which has already manifested its willingness to participate in CLEVER, and IKEA, which has collaborated with the UNEP-WCMC previously.

Civil Society Organisations

This stakeholder segment includes local organisations working on various topics such as sustainable natural resource governance, land rights protection and environmental justice, and community empowerment. Forestry and Rural Development organisation FODER is the head of civil society efforts in the country to promote legality in the forest sector. The segment contains several other flagship NGOs working in the field, for instance CED (Centre for Development and the Environment), FLAG (Field Legality Advisory Group) which is working to prevent irregular logging, and CAM-Ecology (improving the living conditions of local populations). REFACOF - aiming to contribute to forest governance and promote women's rights, and APIFED, a community-based organisation supporting the empowerment and integration of women and young people in natural resources management, are also included in the map. This stakeholder category also includes the associations for the timber industry and processors: The Cameroonian Federation of Associations and Practitioners of Second Timber Processing (FECAPROBOIS) and the Cameroon Timber Industry Association (GFBS).

Certifying Bodies

In addition to the well-known international timber certifying body FSC, other relevant groups are incorporated, namely the Timber Origin and Legality system – OLB, or Origine et Légalité des Bois, that is applied in Central- and West-African countries. OLB was established by Bureau Veritas.

Research & Universities

University of Dschang in Cameroon and the European Forest Institute (EFI) are CLEVER project partners working with local ties. There are also several other research and education institutes in the forest sector in Cameroon and France, including the National Forestry School (ENEF MBALMAYO), the Regional Centre for Specialised Education in Forestry and Wood Agriculture in Yaoundé (CRESA FORET BOIS).

Policy level

The policy level is divided to two sections: state actors, and international organisations and institutes providing technical support for the timber sector. The state actors include several ministries, such as the Ministry of Forests and Wildlife (MINFOF) and the Ministry of Environment, Nature Protection and Sustainable Development (MINEPDED), as well as the Ministry of Trade (MINCOMMERCE). In addition, there are other government offices such as the Timber Promotion Centre (Centre De Promotion Du Bois). International and technical stakeholders include organisations of the importer countries, alike The Directorate Generals of the European Commission for Trade and Environment.

Fishmeal and Fish Oil on a Global Context

Partners at the University of Bonn (UoB) provided advice on the development of a stakeholder map for fishmeal and fish oil through a global approach. This is considering that (i) between 20015 and 2020, the main suppliers of fishmeal and fish oil to the European Union by volume were spread in different regions, namely Peru, Norway, and Morocco (EUMOFA, 2021), and (ii) the stakeholders identified encompass larger sectorial organisations with a broader geographical dispersion between their members.

Figure 5: CLEVER's impact network for global fishmeal and fish oil trade.

Abbreviations in the figure: **Civil Society Organisations:** WWF (World Wide Fund for Nature); **Certifying Bodies:** ASC (Aquaculture Stewardship Council); MSC (Marine Stewardship Council); **Policy level:** EUMOFA (The European Market Observatory for fisheries and aquaculture); UNECE (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe)

Production

The IFFO (The Marine Ingredients Organisation) is an international Fishmeal and Fish Oil Organisation whose network includes primary producers, traders, feed producers, fish oil refiners, labs and certifiers, fish farmers, shippers, retailers, financial institutions, governmental and non-governmental organisations. The member organisations cover over 50% of the world's fishmeal and fish oil value chain. The members of IFFO are complied with its Code of Conduct about integrity, ethical firm behaviour, environment protection, and labour rights. Its wide membership coverage allows for high impact and valuable first-hand data access.

Processing and Trade & Distribution

IFFO also covers the steps "Processing" and "Trade & Distribution". In addition, the European Fish Processors Association (AIPCE-CEP) and the international Seafood Importers & Processors Alliance (SIPA) were added.

Retail & Consumption

Most of fishmeal and fish oil products are processed into animal feed (fish, porciculture and poultry). Fishmeal and fish oil are also used for human consumption via nutraceutical products. This stage of the value chain will be further analysed by CLEVER's partners in UoB.

Civil Society Organisations

Through UoB exploration of the value chain, the maps aim to include Fishermen Associations and Unions -organisations that represent the fisheries communities with scopes varying from local to regional levels (e.g., Caribbean Network of Fisherfolk Organisations).

Certifying Bodies

The mapping incorporates the Marine (MSC) and Aquaculture (ASC) Stewardship Councils, well-known certifying bodies for wild-caught and cultivated fish, respectively. MarineTrust is an international certifier for marine ingredients, whereas Seafood Watch produces science-based seafood recommendations for consumers and food businesses.

Research & Universities

Aquaculture-related research is carried on in the Institute for Aquaculture at the University of Stirling and the Stockholm Environment Institute. WorldFish, also a part of the map, is an international, non-profit research and innovation organisation that creates and translates scientific research on aquatic food systems.

Policy level

In the importer countries, relevant actors include the German Federal Office for Agriculture and Food and German Federal Office for Agriculture and Food (BLE) as examples of national policy stakeholders. There are also international cooperation, coordination, or policy institutions such as; the Committee on Fisheries (COFI) a forum for FAO members on fisheries and aquaculture; the Market Advisory Council providing advice to the European Commission and EU Member States on fishery and aquaculture markets, and the European Market Observatory for fisheries and aquaculture (EUMOFA) - an European Commission initiated party that aims to increase market transparency and efficiency and support supports business and policy and decision-making in the European Union fisheries and aquaculture sector. In addition, Regional Fisheries Management Organisations (RFMOs) will be surveyed, these are international organisations guaranteeing the management, conservation, and sustainable exploitation of fishery resources in fishing areas.

CONCLUSIONS

This stakeholder mapping addressed the value chains of soy, timber, and fishmeal, with regional foci on EU trade with South America and Central Africa. It introduces samples of stakeholders that represent the trade supply chains of timber and soy in Brazil and Cameroon to the EU, as well as fishmeal and fish oil on a global scale. The addressed stakeholder groups include biomass producers, processors, traders, retailers, civil society organisations, certifying bodies, research institutions, and policymakers. They represent a flexible core group of stakeholders that will facilitate prompt and effective engagement and allow us to collaborate with a diverse and integrated set of representatives in the next phases of the CLEVER project. Groups mapped serve as a non-exhaustive sample that seeks to display CLEVER's impact network, consolidating an extended vision of the project's partners and their previously established links to engage with key agents for change.

The support of local partners and research institutions was and will continue to be paramount for understanding the nuances of CLEVER's value chains. Partners like the EFI, the University of Dschang, the University of Bonn, and the University of Freiburg will elaborate upon this work using the stakeholder engagement to develop in-depth and comprehensive value chain maps with detailed breakdown for their stages, along with the policy instruments that interact with them. Other local institutions may be also of help in establishing additional links with local actors.

Therefore, this work lays foundations for the next stages of the project. The findings highlight the importance of understanding the local operational environment and its dynamics. In Brazil, for example, soya is mainly cultivated on large industrial plantations, which makes it orderly to contact corporations and industrial organisations as an entry point. In the case of Cameroon, it is crucial to understand the multidimensionality of the local operational environment, with enterprises of different sizes, and varying degrees of formality. With this in mind, it smaller businesses must be taken into account to ensure a balanced representation of stakeholders.

The value chains analysed display structural differences regarding the prominence of small holders or larger producers, their horizontal integration, and even the scale of irregular production. In the case of Brazil, this initial examination indicates less horizontal integration between production and processing, particularly in the case of soy. The opposite seems true for Cameroon's timber supply chain, where some of the medium and large-scale operations often overlap through categories of production and processing. Although Cameroon's informal sector presents a challenge for the mapping, it may also be an opportunity to engage small-holders and SMEs to gain a better understanding of the impact and points of intervention in these settings.

The trade and distribution stages of the supply chains also showcased clearer entry points considering the larger size of actors. For this, several stakeholders have been identified on the retail and consumption side -mainly businesses with a strong sustainability agenda that have been interested in similar activities in the past (e.g., deforestation prevention). Including this kind of groups in the dialogue, allows CLEVER to interact with stakeholders that often have significant power deriving from procurement policies, and the ability to influence others further down the line through sustainability campaigns.

Special attention was given to including local communities and vulnerable groups indirectly affected by trade, as well as allocating additional efforts to enhance equal gender representation. This is seen through the inclusion of women associations with agendas linked to the supply chains surveyed, and local civil society organisations that work in the fields of land tenure, sustainable natural resource governance, and environmental justice, among others. For most of the local partners interviewed, the issues of environmental and social sustainability are closely linked, which calls for holistic and systemic approaches. Likewise, when considering the policy environment, more attention should be paid to the local branches of multi-level governance at the municipal and regional levels.

This document also elaborated upon the forthcoming methodological approach for stakeholder engagement, namely Participatory Impact Pathways Analysis (PIPA). It is a practical method to allow for the collaborative development of problem trees, project visions, and theories of change. It will be used during CLEVER to enable the participation of a diverse group of stakeholders in the project, but also as a framework for the co-design of the governance instruments that CLEVER aims to build.

All the different characteristics spotted, may allow us to identify potential leverage points or which stakeholders are particularly important to enact transformative change. To achieve this, the support of local institutions, researchers, and civil society is crucial.

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

In relation to CLEVER's Impact Framework, this mapping contributes particularly to the D&E&C (Dissemination, Engagement, and Communication) measures due to their direct connection with stakeholder engagement. At the same time, Table 2 displays a list of items from *Specific Needs* and *Target Groups* to which the stakeholder mapping and forthcoming engagement will contribute to.

Table 2. Items of CLEVER's Impact Framework to which this mapping contributes.

SPECIFIC NEEDS	D & E & C MEASSURES	TARGET GROUPS
<p>Informed and transparent multi-actor negotiation processes to create ownership of knowledge about value chain governance solutions with transformative potential among value chain stakeholders.</p>	<p>Outreach material targeted to stakeholder groups preferences.</p> <p>Preparation of Stakeholder Engagement Canvas.</p>	<p>Stakeholders along the whole trade value chain in biomass exporting and importing countries, namely, biomass producers, traders, processors, retailers, and certifying bodies.</p> <p>Policy makers.</p> <p>Researchers.</p> <p>Wider society including Civil Society Organizations.</p> <p>Traditional and indigenous peoples relying on biodiversity and its services.</p>

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